

Spiro-Compounds. Synthesis and Dehydrogenation of Spiro (5,5) undecanes

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Synthesis of 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9 benzospiro-(5,5) undecane and 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecan-10-ol have been described. Catalytic dehydrogenation of both the spiro compounds by heating with Pd-C catalyst at 360° in a sealed tube gave 1-ethyl-6-methyl phenanthrene as the main product.

Dehydrogenation had long been a very important method for the elucidation of the structure of many natural products. Its place has been taken by various physical methods with much advantage. Of course, this does not in any way diminish the importance of the study of the rearrangement accompanying a dehydrogenation step. This is a complicated method and attended by side reactions. A clear insight into the course pursued by the dehydrogenation reaction in general can be achieved by a thorough study of the dehydrogenation of a wide range of synthetic polynuclear alicyclic compounds. With this end in view we have started this investigation.

Dehydrogenation with Se and with Pd-C catalyst of a large number of spirans had previously been studied by Clemo and Ormston¹, Cook and Hewett², Levitz and Bogert³, Sengupta⁴ and others. Synthesis and catalytic dehydrogenation of 8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecanes with alkyl substituents in the spiran ring had been described by Sengupta and Mitra⁵. With a view to studying ring transformation and also the fate of alkyl substituent present in the spirocyclohexane ring during the catalytic dehydrogenation, we have synthesised 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecane and 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecan-10-ol.

The spirohydrocarbon (V : R = H) was synthesised readily by the following steps. The anhydride of 2-ethylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was condensed with toluene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give a single keto acid, $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-ethylcyclohexane)- β -(*p*-toluyl)-propionic acid (II). This keto acid reacted with salicylaldehyde in presence of dry hydrogen chloride giving a pyrylium salt. This shows the presence of a keto-methylene group and as such excludes the alternative structure for the keto acid. The keto acid on the Clemmensen reduction provided $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-ethylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-tolyl)-butyric acid (III). It was noted that the γ -arylbutyric acid (III) could not be successfully cyclised by heating with 85% sulphuric acid or polyphosphoric acid mixture. It was therefore converted into the corresponding acid chloride and cyclised by the Friedel-Crafts' method to 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzo-10-ketospiro (5,5) undecane (IV). Failure of this ketone to yield a semicarbazone or 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, due to the hindered position of the keto group, lends additional support to the constitution of the keto acid (II) from which it was derived⁶.

The spiro ketone (IV) was reduced separately by lithium aluminium hydride and by Clemmensen method into 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecan-10-ol (V : R=OH) and 1-ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecane (V : R = H) respectively. On heating with Pd-C at 360°-380° in a sealed tube both of them gave presumably 1-ethyl-6-methylphenanthrene as the main product which was an oil with a blue fluorescence. The structure was assigned on the basis of analysis and i.r. and u.v. spectra studies. It was easily converted into T.N.B. complex in methanol which melted at 143°-44°.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Carboxy-2-ethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid required for the present investigation was prepared from 2-ethylcyclohexanone and ethyl cyanoacetate according to the method of Lapworth and McRae⁷ and Harding and Haworth⁸ as improved by Cope⁹.

1-Carboxy-2-ethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid⁵ was prepared from 2-ethylcyclohexanone and ethyl cyanoacetate. It was crystallised from HCl (dil.) in stout cubes and then from petroleum (60°-80°), m.p. 158°-59° (Found : C, 61.53; H, 8.5. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₈O₄ : C, 61.69; H, 8.41%).

The anhydride of the acid was obtained as a thick oil, b.p. 135°-36°/2.5 mm. (Lit.⁵ b.p. 164°-65°/7 mm.) (Found : C, 67.22; H, 8.2. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₆O₃ : C, 67.35; H, 8.16%).

α-(2'-ethylcyclohexane)-β-2(p-toluyyl)-propionic acid (II) : Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (95 g.) was gradually added to a solution of the anhydride of 1-Carboxy-2-ethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (40 g.) in dry toluene (120 ml.). The mixture was kept at room temperature for 12 hrs. and warmed at 60°-65° for half an hour till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The product was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and the excess toluene was removed by steam. The solid product was collected, dissolved in hot dilute sodium carbonate solution, filtered and the ketoacid precipitated with hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 150°-51°, yield 33 g. (Found : C, 74.80; H, 8.42. C₁₈H₂₄O₃ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.34%).

Pyrylium Derivative of the keto acid (II) : A mixture of the keto acid (0.1 g.), salicylaldehyde (0.1 g.) in ethanol (10 ml.) was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0° and kept in a refrigerator. After three days crimson red precipitate of the pyrylium salt separated which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt upto 290°.

α -(2'-ethylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-toluyl)-butyric acid (III) : α -(2'-Ethylcyclohexane)- β -(*p*-toluyl)-propionic acid (II) (30 g.), amalgamated zinc (120 g.), toluene (25 ml.), and concentrated hydrochloric acid (120 ml.) were heated for 36 hrs. The product was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed with water, ether distilled off and the residue was dissolved in hot dilute sodium carbonate solution, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The reduced acid separated as a thick pasty mass, and was extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate, ether distilled off. The residual oil distilled as a thick colourless liquid at 190°-92°/2 mm., yield 22 g. The distillate solidified and it crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colourless crystals, m.p. 144°-45°. (Found : C, 78.73; H, 9.61. C₁₈H₂₆O₂ requires C, 78.83; H, 9.48%).

1-Ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzo-10-ketospiro (5,5) undecane (IV) : α -(2'-Ethylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-toluyl)-butyric acid (III) (12 g.) was heated with thionyl chloride on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed at 50°-60° under reduced pressure. The acid chloride was dissolved in dry petroleum ether and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (7 g.) was gradually added with constant shaking. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 hrs. and heated on water bath at 50°-60° for an hour to complete the reaction. The product was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. It was extracted with ether, the extract washed with aqueous ammonia and then with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The spiro ketone distilled at 175°-80°/2.5 mm., as a light straw coloured oil having a characteristic odour, yield 6.8 g. (Found : C, 84.24; H, 9.48. C₁₈H₂₄O requires C, 84.39; H, 9.37%).

1-Ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecane (V : R = H) : 1-Ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzo-10-ketospiro (5,5) undecane (IV) (5 g.) was gently boiled with amalgamated zinc (24 g.) and concentrated HCl (24 ml.) for 30 hrs. After dilution with water, the product was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and ether distilled off. The residue was distilled in vacuum when it came over at 180°-182°/6 mm., as a colourless liquid, yield (1.9 g.). (Found : C, 89.26; H, 10.87. C₁₈H₂₆ requires C, 89.28; H, 10.74%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of 1-Ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecane (V : R = H) : The spiro-compound (1.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.2 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 360°-380° for 24 hrs. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on alumina with hexane. The first two eluates contained only unchanged spiro-hydrocarbon. The subsequent eluates provided colourless oils which appeared homogeneous by tlc, with blue fluorescence on removal of the solvent. They were converted into trinitrobenzene complex in methanol. The complex was repeatedly crystallised from methanol as orange needles, m.p. 143°-44° (Found : C, 64.09; H, 4.25; N, 9.45%; C₂₃H₁₉O₆N₃ requires C, 63.74; H, 4.62; N, 9.7%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon showed molecular ion peak at m/e 220 (M⁺).

IR spectrum (film); 3100 cm⁻¹ (C-H stretching), 1600, 1490, 1380, 1140, 840, 750 cm⁻¹ due to aromaticity, UV spectrum (ethanol); absorption maxima at λ_{\max} 255, 275, 296, 336, 342 nm (log ϵ 4.8, 4.1, 4.0, 2.5 and 2.4 respectively).

1-*Ethyl-3'-methyl-8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecan-10-ol (V : R = OH)*: The spiro-ketone (IV) (1.3 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (20 ml.) was gradually added to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (2 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (20 ml.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs and worked up as usual. The distillate was collected at 135°-40°/2 mm. as a thick colourless liquid; yield 1.01 g. This spiro-compound was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.15 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 360°-380° for 24 hrs. The product was worked up as in the former case. T.N.B. complex of the third and fourth eluates, prepared separately, after recrystallisation from methanol was obtained in each case as orange needles, m.p. 143°-44°, mixed m.p. of the T.N.B. complex with that of the previous one showed no depression and was identified as above.

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